

DEVELOPMENT OF AN INTELLIGENT STUDENT ADVISORY CHAT SYSTEM

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Abstract— Development of a Student Advisory (STAD) system, which is able to provide responses to students on questions that they would usually ask their academic advisers, is the thesis of this work. A knowledge base was built into the system using Dialogflow - Google's Natural Language Understanding module, which allowed the system to be trained as an agent using phrases or sentences that students are likely to use when communicating with advisors for each context or category of conversation referred to as intent. Information used to build the knowledge base and train the system was gathered from online and offline sources, including the student handbook, students, advisors, and a questionnaire. The information was organized and categorized to determine different intents and possible parameters. Conversation design was carried out to simplify the process and make the system somewhat interactive and conversational using the gathered information. The system was implemented using the Python Django framework and was evaluated using alpha-beta testing. A student advisory system was developed in the form of a chatbot, which is easily accessible, accepting phrases or sentences. It provides most of the necessary information students need to have successful academic sessions on the campus, as though they were communicating with an active advisor.

Keywords— *Student Advisory System; Conversation Design; Natural Language; Academic Institution.*

I. INTRODUCTION

A student advisory system is a type of computer-based or web-based tool that is designed to help students navigate their academic careers, manage their coursework, and make informed decisions about their education. Student advisory systems have been developed in response to the increasing complexity of higher education and the need to provide students with personalized support. They can be implemented in a variety of settings, including schools, colleges, and universities. Academic Advising is crucial and necessary to the success of every student in any academic institution, regardless of how efficient or productive its process is. Academic Advisers (AA) are a very important part of an academic institution as they provide guidelines and counsel for students to assist in their fields of study, not disregarding their other duties as part of the institution.

In the course of studying as students in an institution, the need for an advisory and counselling body cannot be over emphasized across all levels in a department.

This is usually achieved by assigning a specific lecturer as the AA for students in a particular year, to give advice, guide and counsel them on the courses to be selected, the maximum number of units a student could possibly handle based on previous performance, when to re-sit for carry over courses, amongst others; which brings about the necessity of the AA who provides such advice to their assigned students. There is a continuous need for academic advising in academic institutions due to the continuous increase in poor academic performance, which also indicates the urgency for a comprehensive and readily accessible student academic advisory system.

Furthermore, the requirements for graduation of students change regularly with updates to academic syllabus' and it is usually difficult for the staff adviser to stay up to date with this information and as well having sufficient time to attend to every student with the continuous increase in the number of students in academic institutions; which can be overwhelming. The current method of giving counsel to students across all levels in the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU), Ile-Ife, involves students looking for a good time when the AA are available, a lot of tedious movements and physical availability. This is time consuming on both the students and AA; hence, the significance of this research, to develop a system for the department that is easily accessible to the students, that would also provide the information and answers to the most frequently asked questions by students permitting the advisers to concentrate on other tasks of equal importance such as result processing and approving.

However, Academic Advisers (AA) are not necessarily readily available to provide guidance to students due to the weight of responsibility they're saddled with. Therefore, it is essential to develop a personalized student academic advisory system to solve the above-stated problems; this will provide AA with enough time to handle other tasks and also help students save time, with the ease of accessibility and availability of the system. This work aims to bring the necessary general information that is required and also provide course recommendations to the students; thereby bridging the gap between the Lecturer and students. This design will provide timely information to students and prevent possible eventual problems.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a review of existing relevant literature, Section 3 discusses the methodology employed in the

development of the system. Section 4 expounds on the implementation results and the evaluation. The paper concludes and proffers essential recommendations for future studies in Section 5, while the paper ends with the references in Section 6.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

It is crucial that a student receive proper advising, as poor or no advising can have severe repercussions on their progress throughout their course of study, possibly resulting in delayed graduation. In some cases, the advising process may demand more qualitative judgments before a reasonable decision can be attained. This can be due to personal student issues external to the university's academic context. As a result, academic advising does not only entail course advising, but is also designed to support and motivate students throughout their academic life so that they can comfortably accomplish their educational goals. In this light, advisors must have full knowledge of the student's background, academics, plans, and goals in order to give effective academic advice. This may therefore require frequent 'one-on-one' student-advisor meetings so that a relationship can be forged between both parties whereby they understand the student's unique needs. Such advising, however, can be difficult to achieve mainly due to the availability of experienced and committed persons to undertake the task [2].

[1] Explain that the quality of academic advising received by a student is crucial to the overall performance of the student. Good advising yields a good outcome, while bad advising will be frustrating and have a damaging effect on students' progress. However, a staff advisor needs to keep up with the academic history of advisees in order to be an effective guide. Academic advising requires a lot of patience, commitment, and ingenuity, which do not always exist, because humans have their limitations. In many scenarios, the rules for guiding students may change from time to time due to curriculum reviews, changes in course structure, or the circumstances of specific students [4], [8]. This makes it necessary for the human advisor to be adept at all the nuances of academic advising at all times. In many academic departments, the roles assigned to staff may change periodically, making it compulsory for the staff concerned to learn new rules that pertain to advising a new set of students ([5]; [9]). [7] Addresses the bases for the study of academic advising as well as emerging research trends and critical issues, including implications for collaborative inquiry related to student success.

In addition, academic advising is time-consuming and mentally exacting, requiring the application of psychological and people management skills. All of these present a complex scenario that requires good decision-making, which places a huge responsibility on the human advisor. Therefore, there is a need to alleviate the drudgery associated with academic advising by using expert systems to aid decision-making [3]. The inherent learning pressure, the adaptation issues faced by new students, and the shortage of precise future planning due to the closed nature of information sources are common problems existing in every institution [12]. [6] explores historic and emerging trends in the roles, functions, and professionalization of academic advising, while stressing the need for institutions to situate

academic advising within their learning and teaching mission. Along with the increase in the number of admitted students into institutions of higher learning, in this case, universities, there has been little to no increase in the number of academic staff with the qualifications to provide insightful counsel to newly admitted students. Additionally, these newly admitted students are usually unaware of the possibilities associated with their courses of study and thereby end up going with the flow. For example, OAU students are required to register a minimum of 15 units and a maximum of 24 units per semester, most students are unaware of this due to various reasons, hence, they end up registering for the maximum number of units which they're usually incapable of handling; setting them up for failure.

Perhaps, the academic staff who are mostly in contact with students in a department is the Principal Academic Adviser (PAA). This is the person charged with the responsibility of giving the most appropriate advice and encouragement to help students make the best decisions on all problems related to academics. Due to the cordial relationship between students and staff, a Part Adviser may also extend their duties to attend to students and their sponsors by providing information, advice, and general guidance as and when due. Students face new challenges and tackle problems, many of which they are not familiar with coming into a new environment, in this case a university community; ranging from difficulty in managing their time, the inability to concentrate, inability to understand some concepts, difficulty in reading and inability to cope with the demands of normal university workload. It is natural for students to attempt solving their problems personally, which is highly encouraged. However, when it becomes obvious that such a student is unable to proffer the appropriate solution to their problems, they must contact their PAA without delay, especially on academic problems.

However, the performance of any advisory system will be limited by the quality of the gained knowledge (i.e., knowledge acquisition). The thesis of this work is to propose a modification of the existing advisory process to be suitable for use in the Computer Science and Engineering Department, OAU, in pursuance of developing a prototype web-based system dedicated to undergraduate students' academic advising. The output of the system provides the undergraduate students with proposed courses that are precise and non-conflicting, working as an advisor.; it gives the undergraduate student a plan and advice with the appropriate subjects according to the courses that have been taken, and the prerequisites.

[2] Posits that academic advising is a student-advisor collaborative process designed to enhance a student's overall educational experience by lending academic decision support to them. This is done by analysing the student's academic records and external factors (academic capabilities, interests, daily schedules, and financial constraints) in order to produce customized advice. They detail that academic advising can be categorized into four major systematic models, namely: prescriptive, developmental, integrated, and engagement. In prescriptive advising, students succumb to the direct advice given by advisors, making advisors solely responsible for the decision-making process. The primary objective of this model is to focus on the limitations of the students based on previous results attained by the student in

previous semesters and to provide appropriate strategies to overcome said limitations. Hence, the output or result of the model is measured in terms of the student's grades.

In developmental advising, however, the advisor directs the student to the proper resources, and the decision-making process is shared between both parties, with more responsibility being placed on the student, thus fostering a higher level of 'student-independence'. The primary objective of this model is to focus on the potential of the student. Integrated advising is a fusion of the above-discussed methods. Integrated Advising uses a "case management" approach to help undergraduate students be successful in their first year of college. The Integrated Advising model creates an advising team - customized for an individual student - that may include faculty, staff, coaches, and peers. These customized advising teams provide the student with networked support to augment and inform the work of academic advisors. Engagement advising is typically a type of developmental advising, with increased student-advisor meetings. In this model, students, teachers, and administrators are involved and supportive of each other in the teaching-learning process. The primary objective of this model is to help students identify and clarify their personal academic goals and objectives. This model has some predefined assumptions, such as the student being admitted to university, or the student has identified their academic strengths and weaknesses. This model works based on the experience of the advisor towards various attributes like interviewing questions and style, information about changing courses in colleges/universities. The output of the model is to identify the learning style and competencies of the students.

A Issues in the Traditional Advising Process

Quality academic advising requires qualified and dedicated personnel to be made available for the task. Financial constraints often make it impractical to hire staff solely for advising; hence, teaching/academic staff are assigned this extra task, making their overall duties labour-intensive. While this can cut departmental costs, it raises availability issues as advising times may sometimes clash with an advisor's primary responsibilities, such as teaching, thus forcing them to be unavailable for advising. The quality of academic advising is also affected by the length of time that students are able to meet with advisors. Due to the large number of students per advisor, advisors tend to spend inadequate time with students or rush the advising process so that they can facilitate the load of students faced during the allotted advising sessions. This can be seen during registration periods, where there is always a backlog of students at the advisor's offices.

On further observation of students' issues, the majority of an academic advisor's time is spent responding to recurrent questions, pertaining to handling basic issues such as carry-overs, as well as solving trivial course scheduling issues. Also, when advisors try to spend sufficient time handling special cases, it often results in students having long waiting periods for advising, possibly even getting turned away and having to come at a later date. This is unappealing to students, who may eventually resort to hearsay advice from peers, leading them to make poor academic choices and then having

to meet with the advisor to fix even more complicated issues that could have been avoided.

There is an overabundance of factors that may affect academic advising, ranging from the participation students and AAs involved to the kind of advice the students may require. Fear of Lecturers: Some students may feel intimidated or afraid to approach their lecturers for academic advising. This can be due to a variety of reasons, such as fear of being judged, fear of asking "dumb" questions, or fear of being seen as not capable. This fear can prevent students from seeking the help and guidance they need to succeed academically. Full understanding of Academic policies and requirements: It is important for students to have a full understanding of the academic policies and requirements of their institution and program in order to make informed decisions about their academic path. If students do not have a clear understanding of these policies and requirements, they may make choices that are not in their best interest or that do not align with their goals.

Following the crowd (colleagues): Some students may be influenced by their peers when making academic decisions, rather than seeking individualized advice from an academic advisor. While it can be helpful to get input from peers, it is important for students to remember that everyone's academic journey is unique, and what works for one person may not work for another. Opinions or advice from Senior colleagues: Similarly, some students may rely on the opinions or advice of senior colleagues when making academic decisions. While senior colleagues can provide valuable insights and guidance, it is important for students to also seek advice from academic advisors who have a broader perspective and knowledge of the institution's policies and requirements.

III. METHODOLOGY

This work is an interactive system, which is capable of understanding query inputs (human language context) from students pertaining to student advising and providing accurate and explicit responses in the same manner as an academic adviser would. An agent is trained using machine learning, which becomes the knowledge base for the system, comprising most of the known queries a student could make regarding academic advising and the responses associated with each query. The student interacts with the STAD interface in the same manner they would interact with an academic advisor, as though they were holding a conversation. The procedures employed to implement the system are discussed further below

A System Specification

The system developed is a software program (web application) that runs on all browsers, developed to target multiple platforms, such as Windows, Linux, MacOS, Android, IOS, etc. The Microsoft Visio tool was used to build the frontend of the system, and Dialogflow was used to build our knowledge base. The program runs effectively as far as any device that can support a web browser with full support of Cascading Style Sheet (CSS3).

B Data Collection

For the purpose of this project, the methods used in gathering data include the following,

The **Student Handbook** is a booklet intended to serve as a general source of information for the undergraduate students of Computer Science and Engineering. It contains administrative procedures and regulations in the University with which students should acquaint themselves. These and related issues are documented in this handbook. This handbook is divided into several chapters and sections, each of which will introduce readers to the structure, regulations, and administration of the University, as well as provide some hints on how to handle common problems within the University environment. Students are, however, advised strongly to contact their Academic Adviser before taking any major decision in respect of their academic work.

Interviews: Meeting with colleagues within the department who were interviewed to obtain information and ascertain the level to which they interacted with their academic advisors and how they obtained advice related to their academics.

Questionnaire: A Questionnaire was administered by means of a Google form to students across all levels within the department to obtain relevant information regarding how well they employed the advising of their respective Advisers. Academic advisers within the department also responded to the Google Forms to obtain information on how well students make use of the academic advising resources made available to them. The study ensured that the data was converted to a usable format with all the meaningful features determined and extracted for input into the system from the collected corpus - preprocessing and data cleaning were performed on the data before feeding it into the Natural Language Understanding module used.

C. Conversation Designs

The purpose of the conversation design is to further mimic and/or express the flow of conversation that a student could have with the STAD system within a specific context. The conversations are limited for each context, making some of them extremely direct and short. Figure 1 expresses the manner or direction in which a conversation would flow between the STAD system and a student regarding the registration of courses.

D. System Design

The system makes use of a Graphical User Interface (GUI), which requires a user (student) to be authenticated before they can begin to interact with the system. The STAD system design is consistent across all pages, creating a visual identity and maintaining a cohesive and engaging user experience. Additionally, users can engage with the system across various devices due to its responsive design. The different pages of the system include: *the welcome page*, which gives a brief introduction of the system and provides links to register or log in for access to the STAD advisory system. *The authentication pages*, which allow a user to authenticate themselves either by registering as a new user or signing in as an existing user (i.e., signup page and sign in page), so that they can make use of the STAD advisory system. *The chat interface*, which the user interacts with in the form of a dialog as they would converse with an AA. Figure 2 shows the flow chart of the STAD system from the user's point of view.

Fig. 1: Sample conversation design for STAD

Fig 2: Flow chart of the STAD system

The user starts the application, enters a phrase or sentence (regarding academic advising) into the system. The system checks whether the input sentence matches a training phrase within any of the initialized intents of the trained agent. If it does not match any intents, the system responds using a fallback intent, asking the user to re-enter their sentence. If the input phrase matches an intent, the system provides a response to the user and checks if there is a follow-up intent; if there is none, it ends the context of the dialogue. In the case where there is a follow-up intent, the system continues

the conversation uses the follow-up intent until it successfully provides a response to the user based on their inputs. At the end of each response provided by the agent, it checks if the user requires advice on other issues. If the user does, the system restarts the process. Otherwise, it ends the conversation with a closing greeting.

The system detects the user’s intent from the input sentence. In the situation that a user inputs a sentence or phrase which has no intents that the system identifies, it returns a message asking how it can be of assistance, in

situations where they ask for advice that is not academical, it returns the response, "I am unable to provide responses to personal and non-academical issues, please meet with your academic advisor". In cases where the user makes a typographical error in their input, which is close to the actual word that is within an intent, the system is able to match the word correctly and still provide the appropriate response.

IV SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

The system is composed of the following pages: the welcome page, the authentication page, and the chat interface. When the user is not authenticated, a captivating welcome page with a brief introduction greets them against the backdrop of the STAD system's chat background image, with options to either sign up or log in, as shown in Figure 3. The intuitive design and clear options make it easy for them to seamlessly transition from this warm welcome into the interactive world of STAD, where their academic queries are met with informative and precise responses. Figure 3 shows the sign-up page, which contains a form used to capture user registration details, including their name, matriculation number, email, and password. Users can select their level and academic option from the drop-down menus. For users who already have an account, a convenient link to the login page is provided, allowing seamless navigation between sign-up and login experiences. The login form collects user credentials, i.e., their email and password, for authenticating their access to the STAD chat interface. For unauthenticated users, a link is provided to seamlessly navigate to the sign-up page as depicted in Figure 4.

Fig. 3. System welcome page

Fig 4: system login page.

Fig 5: system registration page

Figure 6: Screenshot of chat screen on user login

A System Evaluation

The performance of the system was measured by means of alpha testing, which was carried out after the implementation of the system by the developer. Beta testing was also carried out with the help of a selected group of 65 students within the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Obafemi Awolowo University in Nigeria, considering the following parameters: Functionality, Accuracy, Natural Language Processing, Context and Memory, User Experience.

Figure 7 shows the response of the testers with respect to the performance of the system based on all the

above-mentioned parameters, with the system obtaining an almost excellent rating across all parameters, as shown in the bar chart. The functionality of the system was tested by how the system interpreted and responded to student inputs, how it handled typographic errors, and how it handled synonyms to parameters that have been defined in the system, as shown in Figure 8. Figure 9 shows the satisfaction level of the users regarding their interaction with the system, with only 16.7% of them being fairly dissatisfied, 50% fairly satisfied, and the remaining 33.3% being completely satisfied with how they perceived their interaction with the system.

On a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 is "Poor" and 5 is "Excellent," please rate the chat system in the following categories:

Fig 7: User evaluation of the STAD system's performance.

How satisfied are you with the functionality of the STAD system with respect to the following:

Fig 8: Chart showing user evaluation of the system functionality

How satisfied are you with the overall interaction with the STAD system?

6 responses

Fig 9: User satisfaction level with the STAD system.

V CONCLUSION

In this research, the aim was to develop a Student Advisory system for the purpose of providing relevant and adequate information, readily accessible and available to students, by accepting user inputs through texts at the level of phrases or sentences. It was important to obtain an understanding of Natural Language Understanding and how it could be used to achieve the aim. A student advisory system has been successfully developed, which is easily accessible, and provides most of the necessary information they need to have successful academic sessions on the campus; information which they would have otherwise sought from an Academic adviser, who may not be readily accessible to them.

The majority of the test respondents (over 50%) affirm that the system interpreted and responded accurately to their queries. The majority were satisfied with their interaction with the system. The result affirms the fact that a good relationship with the course adviser, coupled with a good advisory system, promises to yield improvement in students' performances. This is in agreement with the result of [10], who reported that the rural school maintained high expectations backed by proactive support, and [12], which reports a positive outcome. This system is an essential tool that enhances the advisory assignment of an already overburdened lecturer who also has to be saddled with advisory responsibilities. The system can be enhanced by adding an audio interface and also by including a reminder in the booked appointment.

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